

Estimation of Homocysteine Level in Sudanese Obese, Gezira State, Sudan

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ABSTRACT

Science-based evidence on the association of total homocysteine (Hcy) with body mass index (BMI), as well as obesity and elevated Hcy levels, in the general population has been conflicted. The primary goals of this case control study is to evaluate the relationship between Hcy concentration and obesity in Gezira state in Sudan. A total of 221 participants including 140 obese, their average age was 49.49 ± 12.2 years, divided into three groups on the basis of BMI according to the WHO classification and the groups constituted 44 obese type I, 51 obese type II and 45 obese type III, the control group was normal weight ($BMI < 25.9$) include 81 participants, their age medium were 45.78 ± 22.38 years. Three mL of venous blood from each participant was collected in the morning after a twelve hours overnight fasting in lithium heparin container, then the separated plasma was stored at -80°C for further analysis. Serum Hcy was measured using the enzymatic method by Cobas C 411 analyzer. The cut-off value for normal levels of Hcy is $15 \mu\text{mol/L}$, out of 140 obese, there were 43 (30.7%) having hyperhomocysteinemia (HHcy). The Hcy average increased in obese (12.65 ± 4.9) in comparing with control (10.45 ± 3.8) giving significant difference (P value 0.002). The mean values of Hcy were also compared among the various obesity types. It was found that there was no statistically significant (P value 0.628). Pearson correlation analyses showed that BMI was negatively associated with Hcy ($r=0.027$, P value 0.754). The mean of Hcy was decreased in the lower age group (20 - 40 years), and increased in the higher age group (61 - 80 years) showing no significant difference but age is positively correlated with high level of Hcy ($r=0.094$, P value: 0.268). The study finding showed

significant relationship between Hcy and obesity. However, the Hcy concentrations were not positively correlated with the degree of obesity, further studies are needed to ascertain the causal role of Hcy in the development of obesity and to explore how Hcy is involved in the pathogenesis of obesity.

Keywords: Homocysteine, body mass index, obesity, Sudan

INTRODUCTION

Obesity is a chronic metabolic disorder that increases the risk of atherosclerosis in patients. Obesity is not always a metabolic risk factor; some obese people have healthy metabolisms, but the majority has unhealthy metabolisms. Obesity is caused by inflammatory responses, adipose tissue distribution, cytokine production patterns, and aging(1). Hcy is a sulfurous non-essential amino acid that is formed in the cytoplasm during intracellular metabolism of the diet-derived amino acid methionine (Met). Methionine is converted to s-adenocylmethionine (SAM) in the methionine cycle, which serves as a methyl donor not only in cellular biosynthesis of various compounds (e.g., creatine, epinephrine, carnitine, phospholipids, proteins, nucleic acids, and polyamines), but also in epigenetic modulations such as DNA methylation, chromatin remodeling, RNA editing, non-coding RNA, micro RNA and post-translational modification of histones. S-adenosylhomocysteine (SAH) is generated after SAM donates methyl, and homocysteine is formed by SAH hydrolase liberating adenosine from SAH(2).Hcy accumulation causes the formation of s-adenosylhomocysteine, a potent inhibitor of the s-adenosyl methionine-dependent transferase that methylates a wide range of cellular components. (lipid, DNA and protein) (3).Defective Met metabolism, arising from either mutations in genes coding for Hcy metabolism enzymes or deficiencies of specific vitamin cofactors, can raise Hcy levels. Variations in Hcy levels are known to be caused by genetic changes, vitamin deficiencies, and a variety of other environmental conditions such as increasing Met intake, certain drugs, illness state, pregnancy, and lactation (4).Hcy undergoes either vitamin B6-dependent transsulfuration or vitamin B12- and folate-dependent remethylation to methionine through one of two metabolic pathways. Two pyrodoxal phosphate (vitamin B6), cystathione beta synthase (CBS), and cystathionegamalyase are involved in the transsulfuration pathway, which converts Hcy to cystine(5).HHcy levels in the blood are age and gender related in healthy adults. Hcy levels in men's plasma are greater than in women's, rising from 10.8mmol/L at age 40–42 years to 12.4mmol/L at age 65–67 years. HHcy is divided into three categories: mild (15–30mmol/L), intermediate (31–100mmol/L), and severe (>100mmol/L). HHcy was found in about 5% of the general population, and it has been linked to a variety of illnesses(6).Obesity is frequently assessed using the BMI which is a peripheral assessment rather than a body composition analysis to identify body fat mass. In addition, the waist circumference (WC) is frequently employed to assess the presence of abdominal obesity(7).Middle-aged women are more likely to store fat due to a drop in basal metabolic rate and a lack of physical activity, and estrogen deficiency leading to menopause causes various unfavorable cardio-metabolic outcomes that are associated with obesity(8).3T3-L1 preadipocytes generated and released Hcy and it reached six-fold as they differentiated into adipocytes. Furthermore, nicotinamide enhanced Hcy production in adipose tissue, whereas a NNMT inhibitor reduced Hcy production by nearly 50%, demonstrating that NNMT is a major source of Hcy in adipocytes(9).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design and Subjects

This is a case-control study involved on 221 participants (140 obese with minimum age 19 and maximum 80, 49.49 ± 12.2 ; , 81 normal weight with minimum age 15 and maximum age 80, 45.78 ± 22.38 in Wad Medani town in Gezira state in Sudan from 2019 to 2022.

BMI measurements

Obesity status was determined according to the World Health Organization (WHO) criteria (10). BMI [weight (kg) / height squared (m^2)] was calculated in a standardized fashion by assessing body weight and height. Height was measured when the subject was barefoot and upright. Weight was measured by a 0.1 kg electronic scale when the subjects wearing light clothing. All subjects were grouped into three BMI categories according to the WHO criteria (normal weight: $\leq 25.9 \text{ kg}/m^2$; obese 1: $30.0\text{--}34.9 \text{ kg}/m^2$; obesity II: $35.0\text{--}39.9.0 \text{ kg}/m^2$; and obesity III: $\geq 40 \text{ kg}/m^2$) (11).

Blood Sampling and Measurements

Blood samples (approximately 3 mL venous sample from each participant) was collected from an antecubital vein in the morning after a 12 hours overnight fasting in lithium heparin container, then separated plasma was stored at $-80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for further analysis.

Serum Hcy Measurement

Hcy Enzymatic Assay is based on a novel enzyme cycling assay principle that assesses the co substrate conversion product instead of assessing co substrate or Hcy conversion products of Hcy (Roche Diagnostics GmbH, Sandhofer Strasse 116, D-68305 Mannheim). Serum Hcy was measured using CobasC411 analyzer (serial No.0868-16, manufactured by Hitachi high technologies corporation, Tokyo- Japan). Hcy expected values: $15 \mu\text{mol}/\text{L}$ was used as the cut-off value for normal levels of Hcy.

Statistical Analysis

Data was collected from serological and questionnaires surveys, entered in Microsoft office Excel 2007. Then, data were analyzed by Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) program (version 16). The descriptive statistics of categorical variables were presented as frequency and percentage. Student t-test and one-way ANOVA were used to compare for continuous variables and chi-squared tests for categorical variables. Associations between variables were examined by using Pearson correlation.

Ethical Approval

The study was approved by the IRB in Faculty of Medical Laboratory Sciences; University of Gezira. Permission was obtained from Gezira State Ministry of Health and written informed consent was obtained from all participants enrolled in the study.

RESULTS

A total of 221 participants including 140 obese (23 males and 117 females), their average age was 49.49 ± 12.2 years with minimum age 19 years and maximum age 80 years. Obese were divided into three groups on the basis of BMI, according to WHO classification and the groups constituted 44 obese type one (BMI: $30\text{--}34.9$), 51 obese type two (BMI: $35\text{--}39.9$) and 45 obese type three (BMI ≥ 40). The control group was normal weight (BMI < 25.9) include 81

participants (22 males and 59 females), their age average was 45.78 ± 22.38 years with minimum age 15 years and maximum age 80 years (**Table 1**),

Table 1: frequency, percentage and average of Hcy and Socio-demographic data:

		Case (N= 140)		Control (N= 71)	
		F	%	F	%
Gender	Male	23	16.4	22	27.2
	Female	117	83.6	59	72.8
Age Group	20 - 40 Years	33	23.6	41	50.6
	41 - 60 Years	84	60.0	16	19.8
	61 - 80 Years	23	16.4	24	29.6
BMI	obese type I	44	31.4	0	0.0
	obese type II	51	36.4	0	0.0
	obese type III	45	32.1	0	0.0
Age/years		49.49 \pm 12.2		45.78 \pm 22.38	
BMI		37.31 \pm 4.8		21.10 \pm 3.1	
Hcy		12.65 \pm 4.9		10.45 \pm 3.8	
HHcy		43 (30.7%)			

The Hcy average was increased in obese (12.65 ± 4.9) in comparing with control (10.45 ± 3.8) result in significant difference with *p*.value 0.002 (**Table 2**).

Table 2: comparison of the mean of Hcy levels between obese and control

BMI	N	Mean	SD	P value
Obese	140	12.65	4.98	0.002
Control	50	10.45	3.87	

The mean values of Hcy were also compared among the various obesity types. It was found that there were no statistically significant difference between obese type I, obese type II and obese type III (*P* value: 0.628). The average of Hcy reduce when there is increase in the BMI in the study group and the Pearson correlation analyses showed that BMI was negatively associated with Hcy ($r = -0.027$, *P* value: 0.754) (**Table 3, Figure 1**).

Table 3: Comparison of Hcy levels between different obesity types.

	N	Mean	SD	P value
Obese type I	44	13.10	5.27	0.628
Obese type II	51	12.76	4.21	
Obese type III	45	12.1	5.53	
Total	140	12.65	4.98	

Figure 1: Correlation between Hcy levels and BMI

The mean of Hcy was decreased in the lower age group (20 – 40 years), and increased in the higher age group (61 – 80years) showing no significant difference but age is positively correlated with the high level of Hcy ($r = -0.094$, P value: 0.268) (Table 4, Figure 2).

Table 4: Comparison of Hcy between different age group

	N	Mean	SD	P value
20 – 40 Years	33	11.86	5.75	0.445
41 – 60 Years	84	13.08	4.87	
61 – 80 Years	23	12.23	4.18	
Total	140	12.65	4.98	

Figure 2: show Hcy is positively correlated with the age.

DISCUSSION

In recent years, conflicting findings have been reported about the relationship between obesity and total Hcy levels(12). Hcy levels were measured in obese and normal people according to their BMI.

The current study found that obese had significantly higher mean Hcy levels (12.65 ± 4.98) than control (10.45 ± 3.87), which was agree with study done by Rekha et al(13)who concluded that Hcy levels were significantly correlated with BMI.However Motaung et al (13), evaluated 95 obese subjects for Hcy association with obesity and found a borderline association (*P value* 0.080), with ten(10.5%) obese subjects having HHcy. In the current study, out of 140 obese, there were 43(30.7%) having an increased prevalence of HHcy.

Several possible mechanisms can explain the relationship between Hcy concentrations and obesity, according to a meta-analysis study conducted by Wang et al. first, higher Hcy levels were linked to lipid accumulation in tissues, resulting in obesity. Second, Hcy induced endoplasmic reticulum stress induces deregulation of the cholesterol and triglyceride biosynthesis pathways, causing lipids to be not processed correctly. Third, obesity is recognized as a chronic inflammatory condition. In this view, elevated inflammatory markers (such as CRP and fibrinogen) were observed to be related with Hcy levels. Finally, visceral adipose tissue impairs various hepatic activities via the portal by disrupting the proper functioning of enzymes that remove Hcy(12).

This study found no significant association between BMI and Hcy concentrations, although there was a trend for BMI to be negatively correlated with HHcy. HHcy was likewise found to be inversely associated to BMI by Yingying Wanget al(8). It is widely accepted that having a high BMI contributes to the pathophysiology of associated disorders. The BMI does not differentiate between fat tissue and lean mass. Sat et al. discovered that a rise in Hcy levels corresponds to a rise in total fat tissue percentage(14). Thus, BMI as a proxy for general obesity is less sensitive than WC for central adipose in predicting chronic diseases (15). The group with the lowest BMI but also the highest WC level had a higher risk of mortality, according to large prospective studies (16). Furthermore, a 27-year cohort research found that BMI variability was not related with CVD risk in those with or without obesity (17).

Plasma Hcy levels in the obese group showed an increasing trend with age in this study, with the lowest levels between 20 and 40 years of age and the highest levels after 60 years of age. RanranXu *et al* (18) revealed a similar association with age in their investigation; their findings demonstrated that the human serum Hcy concentration falls and then increases throughout time. They believe there are two reasons for this: it is lowest between 30 and 50 years of age and increases significantly after 50 years of age. First, decreased liver and renal function in the elderly causes decreased Hcy metabolism, resulting in an increase in serum Hcy concentration; second, digestive and absorption problems in the elderly cause vitamin B12 and folate deficiencies, which affect Hcy metabolism. This suggests that doctors should pay extra attention to elderly patients, particularly those with cardiovascular and cerebrovascular illnesses, because a high plasma Hcy level has been associated to major cardiovascular risk factors and endothelial dysfunction.

CONCLUSION

The study finding showed significant relationship between Hcy and obesity. However, the Hcy concentrations were not positively correlated with the degree of obesity. According to a literature review, WC appears to be a more reasonable index for assessing the effect of obesity on HHcy and potential CVD risk than BMI. Furthermore, the cause of the association between Hcy levels and obesity remains unknown. As a result, more research is needed to determine the casual role of Hcy in the development of obesity and to investigate how Hcy is involved in the pathogenesis of obesity, so that a better understanding of the association between Hcy and obesity can be used to guide clinical treatment of obesity and related diseases.

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